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EFFECT OF CHLOR-ALKALI SOLID WASTE EFFLUENT ON NUMBER OF GREEN LEAVES OF A LITTLE MILLET CROP

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Abstract

The little millet (*Panicum sumatrense* Rath ex. Roem and Schult) crop variety SS. 81-1, exposed to chlor-alkali solid waste effluent @ 100 g m^{-2} (treatment - 1), 200 g m^{-2} (treatment - 2), 300 g m^{-2} (treatment - 3) and 400 g m^{-2} (treatment - 4) was studied in vivo at the Agriculture Research Station, Ankuspur in the District of Ganjam, Odisha at an interval of 15 days starting from 30 days after sowing (DAS) till harvest of the crop following the ICAR technology proposed by Seetharam (1994) with little modification depending upon the soil condition and climate of the locality. The Number of green leaves per plant in control and treatments were counted and averaged. The number of green leaves per plant gradually increased from 30 days after sowing (DAS) to 45 DAS then to 60DAS and thereafter started decreasing till harvest (87DAS). Number of green leaves in control and treatments exhibited a trend of control < Treatment - 1 < Treatment - 2 < Treatment - 3 > Treatment -4 in most of the sampling periods.

Keywords : Chlor-alkali factory, solid waste effluent, little millet, green leaves

Introduction

Millet in general is the staple food of tribals and also of the labour class in the eastern part of the state of Odisha. The crop withstands heavy rain and also drought condition to a considerable extent. *Panicum sumatrense* formerly known as *Panicum miliari* is one of the typical minor millet crop grown widely on the hill tops, hill slopes and also in the hill bases. Recently cultivation of this crop has also been taken up in the plains. Compared to other small millet *Panicum sumatrense* has some unusual features. It has the capacity to withstand drought

and water logging to a considerable extent. It does not need crop protection measures. Basically it is free from pest. It does not require either irrigation or fertilizer and pesticide. Simply the tribals broadcast the seed by hand with the onset of first rain and harvest after 85-90 days.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this investigation is to find out the effect of solid waste effluent of chlor-alkali factory on number of green leaves of a little millet crop with a view to management of waste in Agriculture.

Literature Review

The degradation of environment due to industrial waste threatens the survival of living beings. Literature available revealed mostly the adverse effect of chlor-alkali solid waste on algae (Mishra **et al.** 1985, 1986), on fish (Shaw **et al.** 1985) and on rice (Nanda **et al.** 1993, 1994, 1996, Behera **et al.** 1995). So far as the little millet crop is concerned, some work has been done by Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR, 1992-93, 1993-94, 1994-95, 1995-96 and 1996-97) under All India Coordinated Small Millet Improvement Project associated with various cooperative agencies for the development of crop productivity. Most of the investigations are confined to fodder and grain yield. However, no work has been done on the effect of chlor-alkali solid waste effluent on number of green leaves of little millet crop.

Study site and Environment

The experiment was conducted at the Agriculture Research Station (a Research farm of Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha), Ankuspur (19°46'N; 94°21'E) situated at a distance of about 25 km from the Bay of Bengal Coast, Odisha.

The climate of the experimental site was monsoonal with three distinct seasons i.e. rainy (July to October), winter (November to February) and summer (March to June). Out of 863.65mm of rain recorded during the experimental year, a maximum of 28.8 per cent was observed in June. The mean minimum and mean maximum atmospheric temperature recorded during the year were found to be normal. The mean minimum temperature ranged from 15.4°C

(December) to 26.13°C (May) whereas the mean maximum showed a range of 27.6°C (December) to 37.81 °C (May).

The soil was found to be sandy (75%) and acidic (pH = 6.58) in nature. The phosphorus and potassium contents of the soil were high (i.e., 9.0 and 46.6 ppm respectively) whereas the amount of organic carbon (%) was very low (0.35%). The solid waste of chlor-alkali factory (M/s. Jayashree Chemicals) applied in the field soil was found to be alkaline (pH=8.06). Textural analysis showed almost nil of sand, silt and clay. The waste soil exhibited a medium range of phosphorus and potassium contents. The organic carbon (%) of the waste was of very low order (Barik, 2016)

Materials and Methods

Twenty-five beds were prepared following the usual agricultural practice. Solid waste collected from the chlor-alkali factory was applied at the concentration of 100 g m⁻², 200 g m⁻², 300 g m⁻² and 400 g m⁻² and marked as treatment -1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. The soil was mixed thoroughly in each bed and leveled. Five beds for each concentration and control were maintained. ICAR technology proposed by Seetharam (1994) was employed for cropping with little modification depending upon the soil condition and climate of the locality. The sampling was made at an interval of 15 days starting from 30 days after sowing till the harvest of the crop. Five plants were selected randomly from each control and treatments. The number of green leaves per plant was counted, averaged and incorporated in this study

Results and Discussion

Fig -1 represents the number of green leaves per plant on different days after sowing (DAS). It was observed that the number gradually increased up to 60 DAS, thereafter it started decreasing till harvest of the crop. Lowest number of green leaves i.e. 9.2 ± 0.245 , 10.4 ± 0.245 , 11.7 ± 0.353 , 12.4 ± 0.381 , and 11.6 ± 0.354 , were observed in the control, treatment -1, treatment -2, treatment -3, and in treatment -4 respectively on 87 DAS. The number of green leaves in control and treatment followed a trend of control < treatment -1 < treatment -2 <

treatment - 3 > treatment - 4 in almost all sampling periods. This gradual increase in number of green leaves from control to treatment -1, treatment -2 and then to treatment -3 might be due to the application of chlor-alkali solid waste effluent which went in favour of production of green leaves up to treatment - 3. Treatment-4 plants showed less number of green leaves compared to treatment-3. This revealed that the concentration of solid waste effluent applied in treatment-4 was, perhaps, beyond the crop tolerance limit.

Fig -1 Number of green leaves (Mean ± SD) at different days after sowing.

The ANOVA test relating to number of green leaves at 30 DAS, 45 DAS, 60 DAS, 75 DAS and 87DAS as well showed high order of variation significant at 0.001p level (Table-1). This indicated that the variation in number of green leaves per plant was due to the effect of chlor-alkali solid waste effluent applied in the field soil.

Table-1. Variance ratio test on the number of green leaves per plant of a little millet crop (*P. sumatrense*) variety, SS. 81-1 in control and four treatments at different days after sowing (n=25).

Days after sowing	Root length (cm)
30 DAS	F=22.311*** ,LSD = 0.310
45 DAS	F=99.263***, LSD = 0.329
60 DAS	F=76.646***,LSD=0.457
75 DAS	F=121.966***,LSD=0.454
87 DAS	F=85.914*** ,LSD = 0.409

***< 0.001, NS=Not Significant, LSD= Least Significant
Difference (p=0.05)

Conclusion

In this investigation, the increasing trend of green leave number from control to treatment -1, treatment -2 and then to treatment -3 might be due to the application of chlor-alkali solid waste effluent which went favour of growth and development of leaves. Treatment-4 plants exhibited less number of green leaves compared to treatment -3. This might be due to the adverse effect of chlor-alkali solid waste effluent. The concentration of waste soil applied in treatment - 4 might be higher than the tolerance limit of the crop plant. However, this concentration of chlor-alkali solid waste effluent applied in the field would vary from place to place and also from crop to crop because of climatic variation of the place and also the genetic set up of the crop. Besides, the soil quality and soil amendment practices by modern improved technology also played major role in the detoxification of the solid waste concentration applied in the field soil.

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